

**RETHINKING THE CULPABILITY OF ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE (A.I) SYSTEMS UNDER THE
CYBERCRIMES ACT.**

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1st August, 2022

Abstract

Over the years, plethora of laws have been made to govern diverse area of human endeavour such as trade, sports, communication, and even technology. Currently, the unprecedented development of technology necessitates the creation of comprehensive and robust regulatory frameworks to address emerging challenges associated with emerging tech such as data protection, tech-ethics, and accountability. One of the most significant developments in technology is the creation of artificial intelligence (A.I) systems. However, despite the numerous benefits of artificial intelligence, its accompanying challenges cannot be overemphasised. Thus, artificial intelligence remains both a blessing and to a curse mankind. Over the years, the advancement and proliferation of artificial intelligence has led to a global surge in the perpetration of crimes, many a time, as a result of possible malfunction by the AI systems, automated programmes by its makers, or malicious use by end-users. This raises the global question as to the culpability of A.I systems; especially, under the Nigerian Cybercrimes Act. With the application of doctrinal research, this paper analyses the subject matter on the culpability of AI systems and provides logical response to the poser. It also examines whether or not A.I can be regarded as a 'person' under the Nigerian Cybercrimes Act, whether or not an AI system is capable of committing the offenses under the Act, and whether or not it can be criminally liable for crimes under the Nigerian Cybercrimes Act. Finally, the paper ends with recommendations and a conclusion.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Technology, Cybercrimes, Cybercrimes Act, Culpability/Accountability.

Introduction

The positive impact of artificial intelligence (AI) is evident in diverse spheres of human endeavour such as the medical sector, legal sector, engineering, aeronautics, nautical, education and even the agricultural sector. With the deployment of autonomous cars, machine translation soft-wares, robots and medical diagnosis soft-wares in homes, hospitals, and other public spaces, artificial intelligence has truly aided man in diverse facets.¹ In the legal profession, artificial intelligence is deployed for legal research, case management, documentation, case analysis, litigation support and communication.² However, despite the innumerable benefits of artificial intelligence, it possesses some threats to mankind. One of the most fears associated with AI is loss of job, as artificial intelligence seems to occupy all avenues requiring man's manual input. Data privacy and protection is also a great concern associated with artificial intelligence. However, a greater concern seldom talked about is criminal culpability of A.I systems. This raises the question as to whether or not artificial Intelligence systems can be liable for crimes; especially, for the offences under the cybercrimes Act, 2015.

Meaning and Historical Antecedence of A.I

The concept of artificial intelligence holds multifarious denotations and lacks a universal standard definition. However, the concept of artificial intelligence entails the study of ideas to bring into being machines that respond to stimulation consistent with traditional responses from humans, given the human capacity for contemplation, judgment and intention.³ Artificial intelligence leverages computers and machines to mimic the problem-solving and decision-making capabilities of the human mind.⁴ This involves the ability of a machine to imitate intelligent human behaviour.⁵

Historically, the antecedence of A.I dates back to 1950 when Alan Turing, popularly referred to as the father of artificial intelligence, and famous for breaking the Nazi's ENIGMA code during WWII, published his paper: '*Computing Machinery and Intelligence*'. In the paper,

¹ 'A CRITIQUE OF GABRIEL HALLEVY'S MODELS OF CRIMINAL LIABILITY OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ENTITIES' *International Journal of Comparative Law and Legal Philosophy* (IJOCLLEP) (2022) 4 (3) 1-8

² Council of Legal Education, Nigerian Law School, 'E-lawyering: Some Trends and Lessons from the USA' *Nigerian Law and Practice Journal* (NLPJ) (2012) 11.

³ Shukla Shubhendu, Jaiswal Vija, 'Applicability of Artificial Intelligence in Different Fields of Life' *International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research* (IJSER) (2013) 1(1) 28-35

⁴ IBM, 'What is artificial intelligence (AI)?' Accessed at <<https://www.ibm.com/topics/artificial-intelligence>> 2nd August, 2022

⁵ J. KARTHIKEYAN (ed.); TING SU HIE (ed.); NG YU JIN (ed.), Learning outcomes of classroom, Research (1st edn., 2021, L Ordine Nuovo Publication, India) 23

Turing proposes to answer the question ‘can machines think?’ and introduced the ‘Turing Test’ to determine whether or not a computer can demonstrate the same intelligence as humans. The value of this test, however, has been debated ever since.⁶ Shortly after that period, John McCarthy coins the term ‘artificial intelligence’ at the first-ever AI conference at Dartmouth College. McCarthy, further invented the Lisp language. And later that year, Allen Newell, J.C. Shaw and Herbert Simon creates the ‘Logic Theorist’ – the first-ever running AI software program. These events set the stage for the antecedence of modern A.I systems.

In Nigeria, the historical antecedence of A.I is not so profound as series of events unfolded during the nascent period of technology in Nigeria within the late 80’s and early 90’s, during the administration of President Olusegun Obasanjo. However, one of the most remarkable events which set the pace for the emergence of A.I in Nigeria, both for Commercial and private utilization, was the ‘deregulation of telecommunication sector’ in the late 90’s.⁷ This opened the windows of opportunities to people to not only access internet services but also explore other novel areas of technology in Nigeria. This gold rush era of technology in Nigeria transcended into people exploring budding areas of technologies such as Artificial intelligence. Without prejudice to the preceding, it is pertinent to state that AI was already in use in Nigeria prior to the tech gold rush era, but not as advanced and pronounced as modern-day artificial intelligence. Some of these A.I systems was deployed in the health, communication, academic and the legal sector. Presently, numerous government ministries, departments, and organizations in Nigeria actively utilize AI systems and other emerging technologies, such as the Ministry of Communication and Digital Economy, the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology, the National Board for Technology Incubation, the National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion, and the Nigeria Communications Commission.⁸

The Criminal Culpability of A.I Systems

The question on the criminal culpability of A.I has spurred global debates amongst scholars, authors, scientists, and legal luminaries. Evidently, over the years, there’ve been series of recorded events on the commission of crimes by A.I systems. In 2015, ‘Random Darknet

⁶ (n-3)28

⁷ Eboibi E. Felix (Ed.), *Introduction to law and cybercrime*, Handbook on Nigerian Cybercrime Law (2021, Chenglo Limited, Moneke Crecent, Corridor Layout) 21

⁸ Josephine Uba, ‘Artificial Intelligence (AI) Regulation in Nigeria: Key Considerations, Recommendations, Legal Framework, and Policy Development for Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Nigeria’, Olisa Agbakoba Legal.: <https://oal.law/artificial-intelligence-ai-regulation-in-nigeria-key-considerations-recommendations-legal-framework-and-policy-development-for-artificial-intelligence-ai-in-nigeria/> 2022.

Shopper (RDS)', an AI built as an autonomous artist and darknet shopper, purchased 'Ecstasy Pills' and a 'Hungarian passport' on the darknet for display in a Swiss art gallery.⁹ However, it wasn't particularly built to purchase a patented artwork for any person or entity or purchase hard drugs. These two major purchases by the RDS raised global legal concerns such as its culpability on illegal purchase of drugs and breach of intellectual property. However, this A.I system wasn't punished by any means with the tool of law. Ryan Abbott and Alex Sarch writes:

What makes this story interesting for our purposes is that RDS was an artificial intelligence (AI), and hardly the first to have a run in with law enforcement. If RDS had been a 'person' located within the U.S., it could be criminally prosecuted under U.S. law. For that matter, entities involved in this activity other than RDS might also be criminally prosecuted, such as those supplying the bitcoin and hosting the exhibition.¹⁰

This story gives a vivid instance of recorded event of the perpetration of crime by an AI system. Such crimes many a time could also entail a breach on fundamental human rights under various states constitution, as well as international charters and conventions such as the Universal Declaration on People's and Humans' Right (UNDPHR), as well as regional charters such as the African Declaration on People's and Humans' Right. Under the Nigerian constitution, such circumstance could also entail a breach of the right to personal privacy protected under section 37 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended).

Culpability of A.I Systems Under The Cybercrime (Prevention, Prohibition Etc.) Act, 2015.

According to the Black's Law Dictionary,¹¹ culpability means 'Blameworthiness; the quality of being culpable'. It further defines culpable as 'guilty'.¹² This means, for a person to be culpable of an offence, he must be blameworthy or guilty of the offence personally committed. In other words, he bears the brunt of the offence committed by him. Of course, crimes are acts proscribed by the state punishable by written law in events of breach. Therefore, any act or

⁹ Rjun Kharpal, *Robot with \$100 bitcoin buys drugs, gets arrested*, CNBC (22nd April, 2018). <<https://www.cnbc.com/2015/04/21/robot-with-100-bitcoin-buys-drugs-gets-arrested.html>> 2nd August, 2022.

¹⁰ PUNISHING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: LEGAL FICTION OR SCIENCE FICTION

¹¹ B.A Garner, *Black's Law Dictionary* (8th edn., USA, Thompson West, 2004) 406

¹² *Ibid* 407

conduct proscribed by the state, in the Nigerian jurisdiction, must be clearly stated in a written law, and its punishment stated thereof.¹³ Section 36 of 1999 constitution provides thus:

Subject as otherwise provided by this Constitution, a **‘person’** shall not be convicted of a criminal offence unless that offence is defined and the penalty therefor is prescribed **in a written law**, and in this subsection, a written law refers to an Act of the National Assembly or a Law of a State, any subsidiary legislation or instrument under the provisions of a law.

From the forgoing it is evident that the punishment of crimes is only done to **‘a person’** who contravenes a proscribed act stated in **‘a written law’**. Thus, to understand the Culpability of A.I under the Cybercrimes Act, we shall consider the following:

- i. Whether or not the definitions of ‘persons’ under the Cybercrimes Act includes Artificial Intelligence (A.I)?
- ii. Whether or not A.I can commit any of the offenses stated in the Cybercrimes Act?
- iii. Whether or not, from the forgoing inferences, A.I can be liable for Offenses Committed under the Act?

1. Whether or Not the Definitions of ‘Persons’ Under The Cybercrimes Act Includes A.I?

The cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibitions Etc.) Act, 2015, is a comprehensive legal framework on the prevention and prohibition of cybercrimes in Nigeria. It outlines some acts and conducts which may be considered as crimes; specifically, known as ‘cybercrimes. It is a federal legislation made by the National Assembly by virtue of section 4 of the 1999 Constitution, and Part one of the second schedule of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (As Amended).

Accordingly, Section 58 of the Cybercrimes Act defines what a ‘person’ is. It states that ‘a person includes an individual, body corporate, organization or group of persons’. Employing, the literal rule of interpretation in this circumstance where the letter of the law holds no ambiguous denotation,¹⁴ it is evident that ‘persons’ does not include Artificial Intelligence. Accordingly, section 36(12) of the 1999 constitution, provides that only ‘a person’ can be

¹³ Section 36 (12) of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (As Amended)

¹⁴ *Awolowo v Shagari* (1979) NSCC 87

punished for crimes expressly stated in a written law. Therefore, Artificial Intelligence cannot be categorized under the word ‘persons’ envisaged by law, culpable of the commission of crimes under the expression of law. However, this does absolutely not absolve A.I from the commission of crimes under the Cybercrimes Act, but exonerates it from punishments meant for ‘person’. The rationale behind this will be further addressed in succeeding paragraphs.

2. Whether or Not A. I Systems are Capable of Committing Offenses Under the Cybercrimes Act?

The forgoing poser deals with the commission of crimes by an AI System under the cybercrimes Act. It has earlier been stated that only ‘persons’ can be punished for crimes or conducts that are expressly stated in a written law.¹⁵ However, this does not absolutely exonerate artificial Intelligence from the commissions of the offenses stated in the Cybercrimes Act. Some of the conduct, acts, or offenses proscribed by the Cybercrimes Act, *Inter alia*, includes: cyberstalking, cybersquatting, racist and xenophobic offences, conspiracy, aiding and abetting, breach of confidence by service providers, manipulation of ATM/POS terminals, phishing, spamming, spreading of computer virus, electronic cards related fraud etc. However, a pertinent question which must be considered at this juncture is whether or not an artificial intelligence system can autonomously perpetrate any of the aforementioned offences? Absolutely, It can. A good analogy has been earlier mentioned of an A.I system which autonomously purchased artworks and illicit drug from the dark-web for a Swiss arts gallery.¹⁶ Also, in 2022 Nigerians experienced a large data breach by telecommunication service providers. This event was allegedly attributed the malfunctioning of their systems – A.I powered. Whether or not the alleged reason for the mass data breach is true, it does did change the fact that a crime has been committed by an artificial intelligence powered system. Such event is punishable under section 36(12) of the 1999 constitution, and Section 29 of the Cybercrimes Act. But can the A.I system which caused the breach due to the alleged malfunctioning be sued? Absolutely, no! it is almost irrational to think of instituting a criminal action against an A.I of such nature where there no laws within the sphere, because an AI is not a person or human under the Nigerian law. Additionally, it may difficult to prove the *mens rea* (*mental element*) of an Artificial Intelligence required in criminal cases to prove culpability in crimes.

¹⁵ (n-13)

¹⁶ (n-10)

CULPABILITY BASED ON MENS REA AND ACTUS REUS.

In the past years, there've been myriad of controversy about the existence of an AI entity. Futurologists proclaims the birth of a new species on earth, *machina sapiens*, which will share human place as intelligent creatures in the universe. Does this qualify A.I systems as persons as seen in movies? or does this make it capable of proving *Mens Rea* and *Actus Reus*?

A fundamental question in criminal law is the question of criminal liability; i.e., whether or not a specific entity – human or corporation – is qualified to bear criminal liability for specific offenses. In order to impose criminal liability upon a person, two main elements are essential for proof. The first is the external or factual element; i.e., criminal conduct (*actus reus*). The other is the internal or mental element; i.e., knowledge or general intent (*mens rea*).¹⁷ It is pertinent to state at this point that if one element is missing, no criminal liability can be imposed on a person.¹⁸ An entity might possess some capabilities of a 'person' as provided by the cybercrimes Act in section 58 to bear criminal liability which an AI does not possess by law. Therefore, in order to impose criminal liability on a person; the existence of *actus reus* and *mens rea* in a specific offense must be present to prove culpability. A brief analogy is this: a spider is capable of acting, but it is incapable of formulating the *mens rea* requirement; therefore, a spider bite but bears no criminal liability. A parrot is capable of repeating words it hears, but it is incapable of formulating the *mens rea* requirement for libel.¹⁹ Same thing applies to an A.I system. It possesses capabilities to act; although it has a super high intelligence, it does not possess the *mens rea* to act or commit the said offence. A.I works with programmes no matter what purpose it used for. However, sometimes it malfunctions and performs some conduct which may be criminal in nature. Nevertheless, these A.I systems are made and used by humans. Therefore, liability is reposed on humans – the producers, programmers, owners or the end users of an A.I system and not the AI software or systems itself. In other words, *mens rea* cannot be proved on an inanimate thing, but on a living 'person' with blood, veins, and brains to programme or use an A.I system.

¹⁷ Gabriel Hallevey, 'The Criminal Liability of Artificial Intelligence Entities - from Science Fiction to Legal Social Control' *Akron Intellectual Property Journal Akron Law Journals* (2016) 4(2)1, 171-199.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

RECOMMENDATIONS:

It has clearly been established that an artificial intelligence is not a person, it does not possess a mind of its own like human to prove the *mens rea*. Although, the actus reus is present, it will still be difficult and incapable of being sued or being held culpable for crimes. However, certain steps must be taken to curtail the excesses of artificial intelligence, viz:

1. Creation of Legal Framework for A.I systems.

The Nigerian government must endeavour to create laws specifically on A.I. Although, an A.I policy known as National Artificial Intelligence Policy (NAIP) is in progress by the Nigerian National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA), per Panatmi. However, the government must put in more effort to create a more substantive legislative framework on the mitigation of A.I misuse, crimes, and disasters.

2. Engagement in Enlightenment Programmes:

Enlightenment programmes such as the courses on ‘Cybercrimes Law’ and ‘Computer Application to Law’ should be thought and made as a compulsory course across faculties of law in Nigeria and even globally. Also, the courses should not only be thought just at the faculty of laws, but should also be extended to other disciplines such as social science disciplines which could foster the awareness and knowledge of A.I related crimes and will provide avenues for students to think and proffer solutions some emerging crimes perpetrated with the tool of artificial intelligence.

3. Periodic Training of Legislators on Issues and Solutions to Challenges of novel Technologies.

It remains a trite aphorism that no one knows it all. Our legislators are not perfect neither is any legislator or congressman around the world perfect. Therefore, periodic training programmes should be organised for the legislators on novel issues bedevilling the tech world as well as the way forward. This is because some of our legislators are quite advanced in age and seldom pay attention to modern technologies. So, they lack technological ideas on novel technological challenges. Without these periodic technological training it is almost impossible to expect the myriad of aged legislators to provide real-time solutions to issues such as the culpability of A.I systems in any form of crime. Therefore, enlightening programmes and trainings will better equip our legislators for these novel challenges.

4. The use of the Law Enforcement Agencies

The role of the law enforcement agencies in Nigeria is to maintain social order. Therefore, special duty by an enabling law should be delegated to the law enforcement agencies to help curtail the menace of A.I related offenses.

5. Amendment of the Cybercrimes (Prevention, Prohibition etc.) Act, 2015.

Evidently during the making of the cybercrimes Act, Artificial intelligence was not envisaged by the lawmakers. So, there was no mention of A.I in any part of the Act. Therefore, if a new legislation cannot be made for the regulation and prosecution of A.I related crimes, then the current law regulating cybercrimes should be amended to include A.I related crimes and its punishment thereof. This will greatly be appreciated by Nigerians, tech enthusiast and cybercrime experts.

CONCLUSION.

In conclusion, there is no gainsaying that artificial intelligence has not positively impacted the lives of man. However, despite its positive impact, it also holds its dark sides and raises concerns as to its criminal culpability; especially, under the Cybercrimes Act. However, an A.I is not a 'person' as provided by the cybercrimes Act. Thus, proving its *mens rea* will be almost impossible. Therefore, it cannot be criminally tried or held culpable for crimes.

However, the Nigerian Government must pay keen attention towards regulating the ever-increasing rate of A.I related crimes. A new legislation should be created and the current laws such as the Cybercrimes act should be amended to cover these novel tech challenges. These should be done with a sense of urgency and zest, as 'a stich in time saves nine'.